

ARTWIN

INDUSTRY & CONSTRUCTION
4.0 SOLUTIONS

ARtwin web portal

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Project Information

TITLE	ARtwin - An AR cloud and digital twins solution for industry and construction 4.0
DURATION	October 2019 – September 2022 (36 months)
WEBSITE	artwin-project.eu
COORDINATOR	Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL ADVISORS PC
CONTACT PERSON	Anastasia Matonaki, matonaki@qplan-intl.gr
PROJECT OVERVIEW	ARtwin aims at improving productivity and product quality, by deploying an ARCloud platform that will offer a wide variety of cutting-edge AR-based services to industry and construction 4.0.
CONSORTIUM	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL ADVISORS PC www.qplan-intl.gr – Greece 2. B-COM http://www.b-com.com – France 3. SIEMENS AKTIENGESELLSCHAFT https://new.siemens.com/global/en.html – Germany 4. CESKE VYSOKE UCENI TECHNICKE V PRAZE http://www.cvut.cz/en - Czech Republic 5. NOKIA BELL LABS FRANCE http://www.bell-labs.com/ – France 6. HOLO-INDUSTRIE 4.0 SOFTWARE GMBH http://www.holo-light.com/contact.html - Germany 7. ARTEFACTO SAS http://www.artefacto-ar.com/en/ – France

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Executive summary

This report is titled “ARTwin Web portal” and has been elaborated as a deliverable (D6.2) in the framework of the ARTwin project, presenting the online dissemination channels of the project, as they were created within the first months of ARTwin.

ARTwin is a Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Action, aiming to develop and introduce an easily deployable platform that enables the design and maintenance of highly accurate digital representations of real environments, be they factories or construction sites (Digital Twin or BIM), that are updated in real time and allow for the deployment of high quality interactive services, well-tailored to the requirements of Industry and Construction 4.0.

ARTwin has established a wide variety of communication channels (official web portal, social media, etc.) in order to disseminate the project’s main objectives, activities, events, achievements and results. In this direction, the deliverable is organised in four main sections. It starts by introducing the current report and proceeds by describing the project’s web portal and key social media, before ultimately concluding with the deductions resulting from the elaboration of the report.

1. Introduction

The current report on the ARTwin Web Portal has been elaborated within the framework of the ARTwin project, which is co-funded by the European Union’s Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 856994. ARTwin is set on providing the European Industry and Construction 4.0 ecosystem with a sovereign ARCloud platform that meets their ever-growing needs for increased productivity, improved product quality as well as reduced time and cost.

To this end, the main aim of ARTwin is to research and develop a system able to continuously maintain a Digital Twin or BIM model that is as close as possible to the factory or the construction site in order to deploy a wide range services such as AR devices localization and Digital Twin/ BIM real-time update. In order to account for the wide variety of AR devices and address complex use cases, processing, mapping or rendering will be able to be distributed and orchestrated on the cloud thanks to a 5G communication. In order to validate the benefits of an ARCloud dedicated to industry and construction 4.0, the project will deploy three demonstrators which will benefit from ARTwin’s platform. Through these three demonstrators, the project aims to prove the gains in productivity and quality as well as the pain removal provided by such an AR cloud technology.

In this context, this report constitutes a detailed description of the ARTwin web portal and presents the functionalities of the webpage together with the social media accounts that have been established for the needs of the project. The web portal along with the established social media channels of the project will be optimised and enhanced with essential dissemination material, which is expected to serve as a multiplier of the project’s main ambitions and objectives. With that in mind, the following table outlines the key online communication channels utilized in the framework of the ARTwin project.

Table 1. ARTwin’s main communication channels

Channel	URL
Web portal	https://artwin-project.eu/
Twitter account	https://twitter.com/ArtwinProject
Facebook account	https://www.facebook.com/ARTwin-Project-110545737082313/
LinkedIn account	https://www.linkedin.com/company/34604402/

All the above-mentioned online communication channels are expected to contribute greatly to the dissemination of the project results and outcomes. In this initial stage, the communication channels were selected in order to cover the majority of online social media and are expected to be active during the entire timeline of the project and after its completion. With that in mind, this report encompasses the following:

- **Chapter 1** states a brief description of ARTwin’s online presence and introduces its web portal together with the social media accounts that have been assigned to the project.
- **Chapter 2** describes the web portal that was created in order to support all the necessary horizontal activities of the project.
- **Chapter 3** describes the channels to be employed for efficient dissemination, awareness raising and communication through online social media.
- **Chapter 4** details the conclusions resulting from the development of the deliverable.

2. ARTwin web portal

The ARTwin web portal is publicly available at <https://artwin-project.eu/> and it was designed during the early stages of the project, in order to support all the necessary horizontal activities of the project. The ARTwin web portal is based on a common layout that is responsive and guarantees easy browsing through the site's web pages. More specifically the layout is presented in Figure 1, Figure 2 and Figure 3 and consists of:

- The **Header** section, which contains the project logo and its acronym, as well as the **Main Navigation Menu**, which facilitates the fast browsing between the different sections of the web portal.
- The **Main Content Area**, the main part of every page, presenting the users' information requested.
- The **Footer** containing the social media links, the structure of the web portal (sitemap) and the information about the project's funding by the European Union's Horizon 2020 framework.

Figure 1. ARTwin web portal layout (top)

Our Aim

ARTwin aims at improving productivity and product quality, by deploying an ARCloud platform that will offer cutting-edge AR-based services, well-tailored to the requirements of European Industry and Construction 4.0.

- Increased productivity
- Improved product quality
- Proactive problem detection
- Assisted problem solving
- Reduced production time and cost

- Efficient constructing
- Considerable time saved
- Automatic detection of defects
- Risks severely minimized
- Better informed decision making

Use case: AR enabled worker

This demonstrator will be installed in a SIEMENS factory and will showcase the AR enabled factory worker. Factory workers will see all sorts of relevant information about the machine they are interacting with in a glance! On top of that, problem detection and assisted problem solving will allow workers make critical decisions in seconds, not minutes!

[Read more](#)

Use case: AR based factory planning

This use case demonstrator will be installed in a SIEMENS factory to enable dynamic production line planning. Using our real-time AR interface to factory planning tools, the production line planning and re-adaptation will no longer be carried out in separate rooms far away from the production. Instead, it will happen interactively on the field!

[Read more](#)

Use case: AR/VR assisted construction

This use case demonstrator will be deployed in the Eiffage Bretagne construction in Dinard, France. Using AR devices, construction workers will have a consistent AR view of the construction and will be constantly receiving all the necessary information and feedback from their supervisor, whether s/he is in the field or not! Workers will save time and minimize defects as they are quickly doing the right job the very first time!

[Read more](#)

Latest news

ARTwin's kick-off meeting in Rennes, France

admin, 14/01/2020, News, 0

ARTwin project was kicked off! The project has finally taken off in Rennes during a two-day kick-off. The meeting...

1 like

[Read more](#)

Our Partners

Figure 2. ARTwin web portal layout (centre)

Figure 3. ARTwin web portal layout (bottom)

The content and structure of the ARTwin web portal was organized and designed to showcase the project, in terms of goals, background, services, use cases as well as the presentation of news related to ARTwin’s work. Site visits, statistics and other information on visitor’s views (e.g. number of pages per visit, time on site, most viewed pages, etc.) will be measured using Google Analytics. The following list presents the main sections of the portal, which are further analysed in the following subsections:

- **Home:** The homepage holds a header menu as well as presents a slideshow, the project’s aim, the benefits it offers to industry and construction, the use cases, the latest project news, a Twitter feed of ARTwin’s latest tweets and slider with the project partners. The main purpose of this page is to summarize the project offerings and current state in a glance.
- **The project:** This section aims to present briefly all the important information related to the project. More specifically, the subsections are presented below.

- **Concept & Objectives:** This section presents ARTwin’s overall concept in a nutshell as well as the cornerstone objectives that will define the outcomes of the project.
- **The team:** The purpose of this section is to present the project’s consortium.
- **Advisory Board:** This section gives visibility to the members of ARTwin’s Advisory Board.
- **ARTwin Platform:** This section is set on demonstrating the ARTwin platform along with its main services, as described below.
 - **The platform:** This page gives an overview of the functionalities of the ARTwin platform.
 - **Unified global map:** This page introduces the “Unified global map” service, which will be delivered by the ARTwin platform.
 - **Localisation for AR devices:** This sub-section gives some introductory information about the “Localisation for AR devices” service.
 - **3D Digital Twin/ BIM update:** This page presents the “3D Digital Twin/ BIM update” service along with its main characteristics.
 - **AR remote rendering:** This page demonstrates the “AR remote rendering” service as well as the main benefits stemming from its delivery.
- **Use cases:** The main aim of this sub-section is to demonstrate the 3 pilot cases that will be implemented in the context of ARTwin.
 - **AR enabled factory worker:** This page gives information about the demonstrator that will be installed in a SIEMENS factory and will showcase the AR enabled factory worker.
 - **AR based factory planning:** This page introduces the use case demonstrator which will be installed in a SIEMENS factory and will leverage the ARTwin technologies to showcase dynamic production line planning.
 - **AR/ VR assisted construction:** This page presents the use case demonstrator which will be deployed in the Eiffage Bretagne construction in Dinard, France and it will showcase the ARTwin technologies that will help the workers to construct more efficiently.
- **Downloads:** This sub menu is set on giving access to the project’s public reports, publications and promotional material.
 - **Reports:** List of public deliverables together with download links for each one after their successful completion.
 - **Publications:** List of publications stemming from the scientific research conducted by the project partners in the framework of ARTwin.
 - **Promotional material:** List of the promotional material (leaflet, poster, etc.) developed for the communication and dissemination of the project.
- **News:** This sub menu aims to serve as the main getaway to the project’s news as well as give access to ARTwin’s newsletter.
 - **News:** This page contains a list of news related to the project, with a view to sharing experiences and achievements between the partners and the community of web portal users.

- **Newsletter:** In this page, the web portal visitors can see all the project newsletters as well as subscribe to the project’s newsletter in order to receive future editions through mail when they are available. The project’s newsletter is delivered through the Mailchimp tool¹, as explained in “D6.1 Dissemination, Awareness Raising and Communication Plan”.
- **Relevant initiatives:** This section presents several related projects along with the links to their individual web portals.
- **Contact:** This sub menu offers the web portal’s users the possibility to contact the project partners as well as get informed about the privacy and cookie policy of the portal.
 - **Contact us:** In this section, the web portal visitors are able to communicate with a representative of the project’s consortium by filling out their comment/ query in a dedicated form.
 - **Privacy and Cookie Policy:** This section contains the Privacy and Cookie Policy of the ARTwin web portal. In general, when new users visit the ARTwin web portal a pop-up message appears in the bottom of the homepage, enabling the users to get informed about the Privacy and Cookie Policy as well as manage their cookie settings if they wish.

Figure 4. Pop-up message for cookie settings

Screenshots of web portal’s pages are provided below, as they appear to the user:

Concept

ARTwin is set on providing the European Industry and Construction 4.0 ecosystem with a sovereign ARCloud platform that meets their ever-growing needs for increased productivity, improved product quality as well as reduced time and cost.

To this end, the main concept of ARTwin is to research and develop a system able to continuously maintain a Digital Twin or BIM model that is as close as possible to the factory or the construction site in order to deploy a wide range of services such as AR devices localization and Digital Twin/BIM real-time update.

In order to account for the wide variety of AR devices and address complex use cases, processing, mapping or rendering will be able to be distributed and orchestrated on the cloud thanks to a 5G communication.

In order to validate the benefits of an ARCloud dedicated to industry and construction 4.0, the project will deploy three demonstrators which will benefit from ARTwin's platform. Through these three demonstrators, the project aims to prove the gains in productivity and quality as well as the pain removal provided by such an AR cloud technology.

Objectives

The main objectives of ARTwin are:

- To introduce an easily deployable platform that enables the design and maintenance of highly accurate real-time digital representations of large-scale real environments.
- To develop and deploy high quality interactive services set on improving business performance and well-tailored to the requirements of professional and industrial contexts.
- To demonstrate and validate the benefits of the ARCloud in major factories and construction sites, by deploying three demonstrators that will prove the quality and productivity gains.
- To contribute to standardization activities, by providing specifications of unified APIs and data representations, fostering in this way a growing and sustainable AR ecosystem in Europe.

Ultimately, we want to enable a wider deployment of AR services into factories and construction sites, which will reduce cost, save time, increase productivity and product quality, in other words, will improve the competitiveness of European industries!

Figure 5. Concept and Objectives web page

¹ To find out more about the Mailchimp tool, please visit <https://bre.is/WYSdSo6G>

Figure 6. The team web page

Christine Perey

CEO, PEREY Research & Consulting, Switzerland

Christine Perey is an industry analyst, researcher and an advocate for interoperable Augmented Reality. From 2009-2016, she led the grassroots community dedicated to this purpose. She is on numerous boards and standards groups. She is the founder of the AR for Enterprise Alliance (AREA) and chairs the Research Committee. Since 2018, she is a founder of the Open AR Cloud association and serves on the governing board. She co-chairs the Reality Capture, Indexing, Mapping and GeoPose Working Group.

Thomas Bierhoff

Head of technology in Atos, Germany

Dr.-Ing. Thomas Bierhoff holds a M.Sc. and Ph.D. in electrical engineering and information technologies and has over 18 years of working experience in R&D. In 2015 he took over the head of technology for the Atos business unit Civil and National Security being responsible for innovative technology and solution portfolio development. Since 2016 he leads in parallel a global Atos investment program for strategic technology portfolio and offering development in the domain of digital transformation of industrial field services and operations.

Figure 7. The Advisory Board web page

The ARTwin platform will be an autonomous and transportable all-in-one 5G solution, dedicated to the deployment of the AR-based services developed by the project. ARTwin platform will account for the available technological capabilities and infrastructure (e.g. processing power, visual sensors, etc.) of the user, enabling optimal and cost-effective service delivery and seamless high-resolution AR experiences across different devices.

The platform will maintain in real-time the Digital Twin of the factory or BIM of the building, using the vision sensors available in the factory or the construction site. The platform will provide an immersive visualisation of this Digital Twin or BIM to:

- Design offices of the factory to facilitate remote production line planning.
- To field-level planners of the factory to allow for on-site production line planning
- To factory workers to provide them with relevant contextual information about the machines they interact with (operate, maintain, monitor, etc.) to support fast decision making and assisted problem solving.
- To construction workers to give them all the necessary information about the tasks they undertake as well as feedback from their supervisors.
- To construction managers allowing them to detect construction defects as soon as they occur as well as to compute the construction progress.

All the above will be realized thanks to the ARTwin platform's 4 unique offerings:

- A unified and standardised map of the factory or the construction site
- A real-time and robust localization system for AR devices
- A real-time update of the Digital Twin or BIM based on the unified global map
- Display of complex augmentations on low-resources AR devices

Figure 8. The platform web page

Unified global map

The unified map will be a digital representation of the physical state of the geometry of various elements making up a factory or a construction site. The map will be stored in the cloud and have the capacity to be both used by various connected devices and updated in real-time by a large number of heterogeneous devices equipped with vision and/ or inertial sensors.

To address the needs of modern factories and constructions, the map will have the following main specifications:

- Useable by a wide variety of AR devices: The map format will allow a map extraction appropriate to the AR device capabilities.
- Persistent: The map will keep a history of changes that will allow to replay the evolution of the captured environment.
- Responsive to dynamic environments: As elements appear, disappear or move in a factory or in a construction site with a varied temporality, applications using this map will be able to query the current status of the map in real-time.
- Fitting to large-scale environments: The map will be scalable enough to cover a large area such as a full factory or construction site.

Figure 9. The unified global map web page

Localisation for AR devices

The AR localisation service is set on maintaining a consistent and unified visualisation of the map, by being able to determine the accurate location of each device accessing the map.

The system will be robust to large variability of the environment. In this context we aim at gradually changing factory and construction layout (e.g. reconstructing the layout of the manufacturing lines, continuous progress in construction), allowing for occlusions by distractors (e.g. moving people, traffic, temporary supporting structures) and variations of sensing conditions (e.g. change of lighting and weather changes, etc.). The pose of the observer will be estimated in real time by integrating camera tracking localisation and information about the environment represented by the map.

Figure 10. The localisation for AR devices web page

3D Digital Twin/ BIM update

This service will provide a real time update of Digital Twin of the factory or the BIM of the construction, based on the unified global map. In this context, our system will track the changing layout of the factory or construction scene, including its constituent objects, by recognizing the changes in the current status of the map, as well as detecting new unknown structures that are not yet represented in Digital Twin or BIM.

The map will therefore provide the current status of building structures, including their components, as well as a 3D localization of objects in the building, by exploiting the dominant parts of the environment remain unchanged.

In addition, a refinement mechanism for the model will be provided by which the detected deviations are fed back into the map and model of the factory or construction, supporting live human-based updates to the map, in addition to fully automatic updates.

For example, a mobile AR device worn by an operator, highlights a previously detected deviation between the current layout and the previous model in the Digital Twin. The user can then annotate these differences, e.g. using gesture or voice input – "these are spare parts for the new machine which will be delivered tomorrow".

This combination of automated sensor-based updates and human-based updates in AR will provide an efficient, largely automated and effective method of keeping the Digital Twin or BIM on the map up to date. The entire process becomes much faster than it was before, as map changes are performed in seconds, not hours.

Figure 11. The 3D digital twin/ BIM update services web page

AR remote rendering

This service will be delivered with a view to overcoming the limitation of computational power of existing and future devices (e.g. smart glasses, tablets, smartphones, etc.) in visualizing 3D information, regardless of the amount of data.

One of the most common requests of every industrial user is the visualization of 3D content. Whether it is for design review, prototyping, visual support during complicated work processes, or simply for optimized communication and collaboration purposes, visualization is an essential part of implementing AR solutions.

However, if we look at AR enabled devices such as smart glasses, smartphones or tablets, the limit of computational power and memory immediately comes up as a very constraining factor to visualizing 3D content.

In order to fit within the memory capacity of these devices and allow applications to run smoothly, this service will outsource demanding work processes like content rendering. This means that the computing power will not come from the devices itself, but instead it will come from an external server which can more efficiently complete the processing.

Ultimately, our remote rendering service will allow rendering and display of complex content in less than 20ms!

Figure 12. The AR remote rendering service web page

Use case: AR enabled factory worker

This demonstrator will be installed in a SIEMENS factory and will showcase the AR enabled factory worker.

In this use case, the factory workers will see all sorts of relevant information about the machine they are interacting with (operating, maintaining, monitoring, etc.) at a glance! For example, they will be able to see a decomposition of the machine's parts, simulation models of the machine's past history, projections for the operation of the machine, etc.

The information will help the workers to immediately understand the status of the machine, and they will be actionable! The AR system will show possible solutions to an upcoming problem, while these solutions may come from real-time simulation models based on the current Digital Twin of the production system, but also from recorded experience from other operators, e.g. recorded videos of how to fix a machine of this model.

Factory workers will be provided with contextual information about the machinery on a wearable device so that they can retrieve and consume the information in a handsfree manner, with a view to uninterruptedly performing the required tasks. The relevant information will be attached to the machines and will be displayed at the best suitable virtual position.

The real time-updating of the factory map will allow for the seamless augmentation of information regardless of the changes in the factory environment (relocation of machinery, change in lights, occlusions, etc.).

Figure 13. The AR enabled factory worker web page

Use case: AR based factory planning

This use case demonstrator will be installed in a SIEMENS factory and will leverage the ARTwin technologies to showcase dynamic production line planning.

Admittedly, Industry 4.0 will make production lines and factory layouts increasingly dynamic and eventually they will change several times a day. The real-time update of the factory layout and the respective machinery on the shop floor is a prerequisite in order to support the flexible rearrangement of the production facilities on the shop floor when a new production batch is planned.

In this use case, the production planning will be done using a VR enhanced planning tool that visualizes in 3D the current layout of the Digital Twin and provides interactive editing capabilities for the planners.

Alongside, this use case will demonstrate a real-time AR interface to factory planning tools, allowing also for field-level planners to use their AR device to make changes to the layout on site!

Factory planning then no longer is only a separate activity carried out by planners in offices far away from the production. Instead, it can also happen interactively in the field!

Figure 14. The AR based factory planning web page

Use case: AR/ VR assisted construction

This use case demonstrator will be deployed in the Eiffage Bretagne construction in Dinard, France and it will showcase the ARTwin technologies by providing AR tools that will help the workers to construct more efficiently.

During construction, to limit the defects and hence to construct well, it is necessary to help workers understand and get informed about their tasks in the best way possible.

In this use case, workers will have a consistent AR view of the reference BIM model at a specific time of the construction and directly on site, through mobile devices or see-through headsets. This feature will allow the site supervisor and the workers to work closely together even if the supervisor is at his/her office, using a VR device.

For example, the supervisor will be able to precisely show to his whole team the next action to do, with additional helpful information (concrete and cement quantity, etc.) that is necessary to its execution.

Additionally, by comparing the BIM-as-built with the reference BIM model, the ARTwin technologies will also enable the automatic detection of the defects and to compute the construction progress.

As construction workers are constantly receiving all the necessary information and feedback from their supervisor, they will save time and minimize the defects, as they are quickly doing the right job from the very first time.

Figure 15. The AR/ VR assisted construction web page

The web pages of the Downloads sub menu (Reports, Publications, Promo Material) have no content at the time of this report, except from short messages indicating that the page will be populated once content is available, and as such it is not considered meaningful to provide their screenshots.

Figure 16. The news web page

Figure 17. The newsletter web page

<p>iv4XR H2020 RIA iv4xr-project.eu</p>			
<p>5G SMART H2020 RIA 5gsmart.eu</p>			

Figure 18. The relevant initiatives web page

Please send us your message by completing this form:

Your Name

* Your Email

* Subject

* Your Message

(* Required fields)

Figure 19. The contact us web page

Privacy and cookie policy

Introduction

Thank you for visiting our website!

This Privacy Policy applies to the ARTwin website and governs personal information and collection usage by the website only. Your privacy is important for us and we are committed to protect it in accordance with the European General Data Protection Regulation 679/2016 (GDPR).

By using this website, you consent to the personal information practices described in this Privacy Policy, which is effective from 17/01/2020. We reserve the right to update or change our Privacy Policy at any time. With that in mind, you should periodically check this Privacy Policy.

Type of personal information that we collect

While using our website, you may share with us, on a voluntary basis, your e-mail address, and name through the contact page of the ARTwin website and/or by subscribing to our newsletter.

Use of personal information that we collect

We may use this information to contact you with newsletters, to disseminate information about ARTwin's activities and results or to promote information from other projects or third parties, which we think you may find interesting. We will not use this information for any purpose other than those described in this Privacy Policy without informing and /or obtaining your consent first, when necessary.

Sharing of personal information that we collect

The website of ARTwin does not sell or lease its contact list to third parties. The ARTwin website keeps a copy of its contact list to MailChimp's server (<http://mailchimp.com>), which is used for e-mail campaigns and newsletters distribution. All personal information included in this contact list is used and protected according to MailChimp's Privacy Policy, Section 12 (<https://mailchimp.com/legal/privacy>).

The personal information collected through the ARTwin website may be shared within the consortium of ARTwin to contact you for specific dissemination purposes. All such third parties are prohibited from using your personal information except to provide dissemination to ARTwin, and they are required to maintain the confidentiality of your information, according to ARTwin's Privacy Policy.

The website of ARTwin will disclose your personal information, without notice, only if required to do so by law.

Storage and deletion of personal information that we collect

Any personal information your provide us through the ARTwin website "contact us" is only used for communication purposes and securely stored on the ARTwin's website email server, only for as long as necessary for us to comply with our contractual obligations to the funding authority of ARTwin, namely the Directorate-General for Communications Networks, Content and Technology (DG CONNECT) of the European Commission, and no longer than 5 years from ARTwin's completion.

You can unsubscribe from our contact list and/or request for your personal information to be deleted anytime by opting to unsubscribe in the e-mails and/or newsletters that you receive from us, or by directly contacting us (e-mail: info@artwin-project.eu).

Security of personal information that we collect

ARTwin's website takes information security seriously and uses reasonable physical, electronic, and managerial procedures to help prevent unauthorized access, maintain data security, and correctly use the information we collect.

Figure 20. The privacy and cookie policy web page

3. ARTwin's presence on social media

Based on the social networking trends, the presence of the project on major social networks and content platforms such as Facebook, Twitter and LinkedIn has been delivered from the early project phases. An account in YouTube will be created later in the project and well before the creation and promotion of the project's videos. To enhance the interlinkage of the web portal with the project's social media accounts, there are short-links to all project social media channels in the ARTwin web portal.

Figure 21. Social media links on ARTwin's web portal

A quick overview of the main social media channels (Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn) that have been created for disseminating the project results is presented below.

Figure 22. ARTwin's Facebook page

Figure 23. Artwin's page on Twitter

Figure 24. ARTwin's page on LinkedIn

4. Conclusions

This report has presented the online presence of ARTwin, emphasizing on its web portal and social media accounts as part of a multi-dimensional dissemination, awareness raising and communication approach that will address all relevant target groups and raise public awareness about the solutions to be created, developed and demonstrated in the framework of ARTwin, with a view to paving the way for their successful rollout and uptake beyond the end of the project.